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Research Article

Analysis Study of Landslide Induced By Earthquake in Tandikat Partamuan Sub District, Padang Pariaman District, West Sumatra, Indonesia

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ABSTRACTS

Earthquake on 30 September 2009 and its induced landslide that happened in Sumatra have destructed many things in Padang Pariaman district and Padang City. Exactly, the location of landslide is in Lubuk Laweh, Cumanak, and Kapalo Koto. In these areas there were 200 people, many houses and schools, and also agricultural lands (sawahs, and ladangs) buried. A research was conducted using survey method, which was done by field observing on pumiceous tuff phenomenon affected by water flow in the study area. Beside that, soil and land characteristic data from previous research were used. Among soil physical characteristic used are soil texture (pipete method) and structure, bulk density (gravimetric method), permeability (Debott method), solum depth (direct measure), and soil organic matter (walkley and Black method). Land characteristic analysis were conducted by observing the field and also analyzing topographic map from google earth programme, land use analysis was conducted by using landuse map. Analysis data of soil and land characteristic were used for landslide grade criterium from Zuidam (1979); Daekombe dan Gardiner (1983); Cooke dan Doorkamp (1994). Based on our field study and some previous research showed that this location has high susceptibility for happening landslide process. It is mainly affected by parent material of the soil which is hornblende hypersthene pumiceous tuff (Qhpt) and pumiceous tuff and andesite (basalt) (Qpt). Those parent materials are slightly consolidated, soft and light. Generally, the top soil has clay, loam and the subsoil has sand as well as loamy sand texture. The climate of the location is wet tropical season which is characterized by more than 4000 mm rainfall per year and evenly distributed whole years. Based on water balance Penman equation, the study area has surplus of water the whole year. The rolling and steep slope (> 45 % slope) hillocky and strongly dissected of the study area were observed in the landslide site. Land use type also promotes landslide processes because coconut trees and mixed garden growing in steep slope. The result of soil and land characteristic analysis showed that soil characteristics of landslide has interval value 13 and land characteristic of landslide has interval value 20. By summing the value of soil characteristics and land characteristics, the total was 33. This grade showed that the risk level in landslide area was quite high. Thus, this study area has high interval value of landslide damage. Besides this site, there are many other locations detected having high landslide damage, i.e Sungai Geringging, Koto Timur, and areas throughout Maninjau caldera.

KEYWORDS: Landslide, Earthquake, Pumiceous tuff, Wet Tropical climate, Soil and Land characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Spectacular earthquake having 7,9 SR which happened on Wednesday 30 September 2010 had epicentrum in Indian Ocean which is about 57 km Southwest of Pariaman within 71 km depth. The earthquake had killed many people and caused houses, schools, dam and irrigation channel destruction in Padang Pariaman, Agam, Pesisir Selatan, and Pasaman District and Padang City. According to Taufik Efendi (2009), the earthquake had killed 1000 people and has damaged as well many houses, agricultural land like sawahs, drylands, and about 650 animals.

According to the head of Agriculture office of West Sumatra (Singgalang 14 October 2009), the impact of earthquake on agricultural land had \pm 88 damage irrigation channel, 10592 ha of drained sawahs, half of the sawahs had found in Padang Pariaman District (approximately 5747 ha). The damaged area was found in

Mentawai district, Padang City, and few areas in Agam district. The problem of the agricultural land will decrease community income in west Sumatra and in turn will decrease food security.

The destruction of economic and irrigation facilities, distribution of agriculture facilities had broken community economy for many years in the future. Thus, attention of government was needed to rehabilitate earthquake impact for all aspects, mainly to improve community facilities such as irrigation facility for agriculture land, and also rehabilitate house, office and school damage. However, the improvement will need high cost. Besides that, earthquake also damage large areas in Lubuk Laweh, Cumanak and Kapalo Koto. Approximately, there were a lot of sawahs and garden, 200 people and few villagers had been buried in the three villages. Amount of the soil having become landslide were estimated about 1.000.000 m³ of buried materials. High potential of landslide event in Padang Pariaman District, based on the result of a study from Japanes International Cooperation Agency (JICA, 2009) showed that there are 126 points of landslide potential event on some locations. Toshiasu Ueno (2009) (JICA Workshop) stated that high landslide potential was found in Maninjau Caldera. There are parent material which derived from pumiceous tuff andesite and hornblende hyphersthene puceous tuff of Maninjau caldera at 500 m above sea level

Landslide impact on agricultural land will involve many factors. Heavy rainfall (> 4000 mm per years) in the location will promote landslide event. It is caused by soil porosity which is not able to infiltrate water into soil profile and in turn, it will promote runoff and erosion. The problem will decrease landuse cover on the soil. Furthermore, agricultural lands are unfunctional to produce staple food crop like rice and corn.

Based on geologic map of Padang Sheet (Kastowo et al., 1996) the landslide area, consist of pumiceous tuff from Maninjau Caldera. This material is slightly consolidated, soft, and light. Thus, the area will be easy to cause landslide again in the future, if the area can not be protected. Forgetting the method to prevent landslide event will be needed collaborative research in the landslide susceptible area.

Based on the above description, landslide phenomenon possibly happen for future, the research will be needed to explain why pumiceous tuff (Qpt) and hornblende hephersthene pumiceous tuff (Qhpt) are susceptible to landslide in Tandikek Partamuan, Padang Pariman District, West Sumatra.

Objective of the Research

1. To analyse landslide phenomena in Tandikek that parent material was pumiceous tuff and earthquake affect at 30th September 2009 and has 7,9 SR magnitude.
2. To analyse the parameters of landslide event in Tanbdikek.
3. To look for possibility effort by doing conservation measures and decreasing landslide dissaater on soil and land physical properties for agricultural land, real estate, resettlement in the future.

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted at Tandikek, Partamuan and Padang Pariman District. Soil analysis was conducted at Soil Science Department Laboratory, Agriculture Faculty, Andalas University. Water analysis was conducted in UPTD Healthy Laboratory Agency, West Sumatra.

The research was conducted by using survey method with travelling all over the study area and by obeserving pumiceous tuff phenomenon which it is affected by water flow and then land characteristics, such as topographic, and land use condition, and the exposure of landslide event in the field. For observing soil characteristics, soil physical data from previous research were used (Yunita, 2003; Saidi et al. 2011). Soil analysis parameters consist of texture (pippete and filter method), bulk density (gravimetric method), structure (field observation), organic matter content (Walkley and Black method), and permeability rate (Deboodt and Gabriel method). Land characteristic analysis was conducted by observing in the field and also by using topographic map derived from google earth programme, and land use analysis was conducted by using landuse map. Analysis of soil and land characteristics was evaluated by using landslide grade criterium from Zuidam (1979); Daekombe dan Gardiner (1983); Cooke dan Doorkamp (1994) are presented in Table 4 and Table 5 and Table 6 (Enclosed)

The analysis of landslide event was done in the field by using different shoting camera for dual time camera shotting.

RESULT AND DISCUSION

Description of Study Area

Geographycally, the study site are located between 0° 28° to 0o 33° S and 100° 09° to 100° 18° E. The administration of study site involves Tandikek, Partamuan, Padang Pariaman District, West Sumatra Province.

The area study site is around 59 km from Padang City and 19 km from Pariaman City. Exactly, study site is presented in Figure 1

Resources: Departemen Energi dan Sumberdaya Mineral. Badan Geologi, Pusat Vulkanologi dan Mitigasi Bencana Geologi (2009).

Figure 1: Location of the Study Area

Tandikek study site is in western volcanic lower slope of Mount Tandikek and a part of Mangau watershed. The study area is passed by Mangau river to west direction until it reaches Indian Ocean. When earthquake event happened material of landslide had covered Mangau River, so that the flow of water of Mangau stopped for 4 hours.

Climate

The study area has amount of rainfall as 4322 mm per years and the distribution of rainfall even for every years are ranging between 171 mm - 603 mm. The condition does not limit crop growth, but possibly will happen to leaching of nutrient. Based on monthly rainfall and yearly data, the study areas are classified as A type (Oldeman, Irsal Las, and Darwis, (1979), A type (Smith and Fergusson, 1957) and Af type (Koppen method). Average temperature are ranging between 24, 0 - 26, 4 °C, Maximum temperature are ranging between 30, 9 to 31, 8 °C, and a minimum temperature are ranging between 21.1 to 22, 9 °C. Relative humidity are ranging between 82 - 89 %. Solar radiation is ranging between 8, 1 to 69 %. Wind speed is ranging between 0,3 - 0,7 m/second. Air pressure is ranging between 990, 7 to 1002,6 milibar and the direction of wind is Northwest. Water balance of the study area reflected differs from the amount of water intake and outake in hydrologic processes. The value water balance can give the reflection about fluctuation of water in the watershed; water reservoir, water will infiltrate into soil, and water be lost by runoff. Evapotranspiration value can be gotten by using Cropwat program from AGLW/FAO method. The result of Etp Penman computation and water balace of the study area is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Evapotranspiration and water balance in Tandikek study area

Figure 2 showed that the study area does not have dry months in years, but it usually has water surplus along the years. It promote to possibly landslide event in the study area.

Based on the amount of rainfall, days rain and highest rainfall in one month can be accounted rain erosivity by using Bols formula in the study area is ranging 277, 11 to 625,62. This data are included high:

Geology and Parent Material of Soil

Based on geology map of Padang quadrangle Sumatra (Kastowo et al., 1996) the most common parent material of soil in the study area consist of hornblende hypersthene pumiceous tuff (Qhpt), and pumiceous tuff and andesite (basalt) (Qpt). Hornblende hypersthene pumiceous tuff (Qhpt) consists of entirely pumiceous lapili, commonly ranging from 2 to 10 cm in diameter, which contain 3-10 % hornblende, hypersthene and biotit, slightly consolidated. Pumiceous tuff and andesite (basalt) Qpt consist of glass shard and 5 to 50 % pumiceous fragments 1-20 cm in diameter, slightly consolidated. There are some volcanic material derived from the eruption of Maninjau caldera.

Geomorphology and Landform

The geomorphology of the study area consists of volcanic plain and lower slope of volcanic mountain. Volcanic plain consist of the area having slope gradient ranging from 0 to 8 % and sometimes steep land such as upper of Mangau river. Volcanic lower and middle slopes have slope gradient ranging from 8 - 45 % . Especially, in the Tandikek area, the slope gradient is ranging from 16 -45 % , but sometimes steeper (> 45 %). Besides that, we found river valley and riverine flood plain in the down of the river which enlarge to the right and the left of the river. In the study area, it was found hilly and hilly landform that we saw near Lubuk Laweh, Cumanak and Kapalo Koto villages. They were called bukit Gunung Tigo, and Bukit Cumanak, Bukit Lubuk Laweh. The hilly and hilly landform happen due to erosion because the parent material slightly consolidated but they have steeper slope gradient (> 45 %). They are easy and more susceptible to landslide induced disaster event.

Vegetation and Landuse

The study area used to have coconut garden, dan mixed garden which were grown by pinang, coconut, durians, and others, secondary forest was found in the top of hilly and hilly area. In the river valley, riverine flood plain, and the volcanic plain were found sawahs, sometimes coconut trees and resettlements.

Land Unit and Soil Type

Based on Land unit map of Padang quadrangle from Soil Research Centre and Agroclimate (1990) the study area has four group of land unit that consists of ;

- a. Vd 232 and Vd 233 land units; Volcanic plain and plato from acid tuff in the rolling (8-16 % slope), moderately desected - strongly desected areas. They are located between 40 -700 m above sea level. Soil type is dominated by Dystrocept that covered 23556 ha or 4,06 %. The land units are distributed upper of Ampalu river.
- b. Vd 2.7.2 and Vd 2.7.3 land units; vocanic plain from intermediate tuff and lava that have hilly landform (> 16 % slope), moderately desected to strongly desected. They are located between 50 -495m

above sea level. Soil type is dominated by Dystrandept that covered 6540 ha (1,13 %). Vd 273 land unit is found in the Sungai Geringging village (susceptible landslide event). Vd 272 land unit is found in Kapalo Koto, Cumanak, and Padang Laweh villages in the area that had landslide disaster induced by earthquake 7,9 SR on September 30th, 2009.

- c. Vab 2.10 .2 land unit is volcanic hilly from intermediate tuff and lava having hilly area with slope gradient (> 16 %), moderately desected which is found on 100 - 2300 m above sea level. The soil type is dominated by dystropept that cover 34689 ha or 5,99 %. The land units are hilly and mountainly land forms which is found in foot slope of mount Tandikek.
- d. Vd 2.10.2 land unit; volcanic hilly derived from acid tuff, slope gradient > 16 %, moderately desected that found in 100 - 300 m above sea level. Soil type is dominated humitropept that cover 1021 ha or 0,18 % from the area.

Landslide Analysis

Landslide disaster in West Sumatra has become into emergence phase. Landslide disaster in Tandikek study area was induced by earthquake dated 30th September 2009. Landslide type that happened in the study area is debris flow. Parent material is derived from the result of the volcanic eruption of Maninjau Caldera, consist of pumiceous tuff, gravel, quartz, volcanic rock, and lime stones moved. The debris flow was triggered by high rainfall at moment. Rainfall will infiltrate and penetrate into soil profiles which will reach impermeable layer in turn play role on as shear plane. It will increase the weight of bulk debris matter on shear plane. By few disturbance (30 September 2009 earthquake as trigger), the debris flow material on shear plane will move to along slope gradient and finally moved to offslope. Besides rainfall and earthquake, debris flow in the study area was also affected by landuse pattern which it was not suitable, soft and unconsolidated parent material and bad soil physical properties condition.

According to Zuidam (1979), landslide processes was characterized by soil and land characteristics. Soil characteristic consists of soil bulk density, organic matter content, soil solum, soil permeability and soil texture. Land characteristic consists of slope gradient, length of slope, stone exposure, water table depth, landuse, and amount of rainfall per month.

Soil Characteristics

Soil types that cover Tandiek study area are Dystranddept and Dystropept. The soil solum depth will be affected by degree of slopes. On Slope 25-45 %, soil solum depth is ranging between 60-90 cm, and the slope area > 45 % usually is ranging between 20-60 cm. Thus the criterium of soil solum depth is classified into code 2. In the topsoil, the soil structure include crumb and granular which it is classified into code 2, while, in subsoil, soil structure include single grain and massive which it is classified into code 4. Soil texture in the study area is classified in silty loam to loam in upper layer. The result of evaluation of soil characteristics is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Result of soil characteristic observation

No	Land Use	Soil Texture					Bulk Density *		Soil Organic matter		Permeability		
		Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Cl s	code	g/cm ³	code	(%)*	code	cm/hour	Soil type	code
1	Mixed Garden	16	73	11	Si L	3	0.58	1	21,10	1	0.79	Dystrppept	4
2	Sawahs	24	74	2	Si L	3	0.42	1	18,92	1	4.07	Dystrppept	3
3	Forest	27	57	16	Si L	3	0.44	1	20,81	1	10.24	Dystrandept	1
4	Cinnamom tree	22	75	3	Si L	3	0.41	1	22,13	1	11.29	Dystrandept	1
5	Coconut tree	30	56	14	Si L	3	0.57	1	19,62	1	4.94	Dystrppept	3

Where: Source *) Yunita (2003).

In Table 1: showed that the evaluation of soil texture is classified into code 3. Soil organic matter content in the study area is classified by high ($> 5,01\%$) include code 1. While, the soil bulk density less than $0,75 \text{ g/cm}^3$ is also classified into code 1. Soil permeability in the study area are ranging between 0,79 to 11,29 cm/hour (Slow to quick) especially for sawah, mixed garden and coconut tree landuse type. It was classified into code 3 and code 4.

Table 2: Harkat Soil Characteristic

The Location of observation	Solum Depth	Soil Texture	Soil Structure	Carbon Organic	Bulk Density	Permeability
Kepalo Koto (Partamuan Sub District (Tandikek)	3	3	3	4	2	3
Lubuk Laweh (North Tandikek)	4	3	3	4	2	4
Lubuh Laweh Atas(North Tandikek)	3	3	4	4	2	3
K PLereh nan Panjang (Padang Sago Sub District)	3	3	4	2	2	1

Sources: Saidi A et al.(2011)

From Table 2: it can be seen that the soil solum depth study sites classified as in (grade 4). Texture land is generally classified as moderate (grade 3) to smooth the sandy clay loam to sandy clay (grade 4). Wuryanto et al (2003) stated that of the field verification showed that the rougher texture of the soil will be more prone to landslides than finer textured soils (clay) for coarse textured soils have lower cohesion. Soil structure in all regions generally range from subangular blocky (3) to single grained and massive (4), and organic matter content is generally low (4), low organic matter content resulted in reduced aggeragasi soil so the soil will be easily dispersed due to the influence of the soil.

Land Characteristic

Land characteristics are factors causing landslides are slope, length of slope, rock outcrops, depth of ground water, land use and rainfall. The results of assessment of land characteristics can be seen in Table 3

Tabel 3: The land characteristic of the study area

The Location of observation	Slope	Length slope	Rock exposure	Water table	Land use	Montly rainfall
	(%)	(m)	(%)	(m)		(mm)
Kepalo Koto (Partamuan SubDistrict)	4	3	3	4	4	4
Lubuk Laweh (North Tandikek)	4	3	3	4	4	4
Lubuh Laweh Atas(North Tandikek)	3	3	3	4	4	4
Kampung Lereh nan Panjang (Padang Sago Sub District)	3	3	3	4	4	4

Sources: Saidi A et al. (2011)

From Table 3 it can be seen that the slope ranges from the grade of 3-4 (27-45%) and length of slopes classified grade 3 (120 - 200 m depth). The role of outcrop is generally considered the grade of 3 and depth of the water table is generally below 250 m are classified as grade 4. Land use is classified grade 4.

Based on our observation in the Tandikek study area, the dominant slope gradient is generally $> 45\%$ gradient mainly for forest, mixed garden and coconut tree landuse types. The length of slope in the study area

ranges 50-250 m. Thus, the gradient and length of slope are classified into code 4 and code 3, respectively. Rock exposure is quite high or it is classified by into code 3.

Based on result of observation in the Tandiek study area, watertable depth is slightly shallow because it was found massive layer in the sub soil. This massive layer is shear plane for landslide event (Figure 3a). The watertable depth is classified into code 3.

Figure 3. (a) Soil condition was eroded by water, (b). Landuse in Tandiek.

Landuse types in the Tandiek study area is presented in Figure 3 b. In Figure 3 b showed that landuse type in the study area are sawahs, bush, mixed garden, coconut tree garden. Especially, the steep areas were found coconut trees and bush. Based on land use characteristic criterium, the study areas are classified into code 3. Based on rainfall data collected in the study area, it was found the amount of 171 mm is the lowest rainfall per month (July) to 605 mm is the highest rainfall per month (September). Thus characteristic rainfall is classified into code 4.

Result of Landslide Analysis

Based on result described above, we can draw conclusion as presented in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4: Total of soil characteristic and land characteristic class code

No	Soil Charatersitic	Soil Properties	Adverbial	Code
1	Soil Solum Depth	25- 60 cm	Shallow	2
2	Texturu	L, SL, SiL, Si	Medium	3
3	Structure	Single grain, massive	Poor	4
4	C-Organic Content	> 5,01 %	Very High	1
5	Bulk Density	< 0,75 g/cm ³	Very Good	1
6	Soil Permeability	2,0-6,25 cm/hour	Medium	3
	Total			13

Table 3: Total land characteristic code

No	Land Characteristic	Land properties	Adverbial	Code
1	Slope gradient	> 40 %	Steeply	4
2	Length of slope	50 - 250 m	Length	3
3	Stone Exposure	15-90 % of area	Much	3
4	Water Table	> 100 m	Shallow	4
5	Landuse	Sm, Kc	Moderately Good	2
6	Rainfall	> 90 mm/month	Very High	4
	Total			20

By summing code of landslide event of soil characteristic and land characteristic was found value 33 (13 + 20 = 33). Based on the criterium of landslide induced factors, the Tandikek study area is classified into high. It means that the soil is weak and soft and often lead to gully erosion. When we go to the field it showed that the depth of gully increased in a short time. The depth of the gully increased around 50 cm in two weeks. Soil textures in the topsoil are silt loam and coarse texture in the subsoil. We assumed that this condition can be caused by the parent materials of the soil which are hornblende hyperstine pumiceous tuff (Qhpt) and pumiceous tuff (Qpt). Thus, landslide disaster will often happen in the study area because, the study area has high rainfall and a lot of steep slope areas and also mislanduse.

Based on the result of Saidi et al. (2011) about why the landslide will happened in Padang pariaman District by using same criterium of landslide damage in the same location. The result can be explained as be presented in Table 5

Table 5: Landslide damage index in Padang Pariaman District

Location	The grade of Soil Characteristics	The grade of Land Characteristic	Interval Class	The Criterium of Landslide damage
Kepalo Koto (Partamuan Sub District)	20	20	40)	High
Lubuk Laweh (North Tandikek)	22	19	41	High
Lubuh Laweh Atas(North Tandikek)	20	21	41	High
K PLereh nan Panjang (Padang Sago Sub District)	19	21	40)	High

Sources: Saidi A et al. (2011)

From Table 5, It can be seen that the level of avalanche danger in the the study area are rather high (35-38) and high criterium (40-42). Description of the level of avalanche danger can be explained as follows;

Avalanche Danger Level is Rather High

Areas with high levels of avalanche danger rather is spread on the area of Koto Mambang (Sei Sarik sub District), Padang Olo (Sei Limau sub District), and Ambacang Gadang villages (Sei Geringging sub district). This condition is characterized by a slope ranging from 25 to 38% belong to a rather steep (grade 3), the type of land use is generally a mixture of coconut groves and gardens (2), while other factors such as rainfall is as the same height and depth of the shallow ground water .

Level High Avalanche Danger

High levels of avalanche danger in the area scattered in kepalo Koto, Lubuk Laweh, Lubuk Laweh Atas, Sarang Gagak, Lareh nan Panjang villages (Partamuan sub district), Kudu Ganting and Padang Alai villages (District V Koto Timur). The dominant factor influencing are slope greater than 40%, the texture layer of topsoil clay and sand on the bottom layer of tuff pumice materials with hornblende tuff hyperstine minerals (Qhpt) and blocky soil structure on the top layer and a single grain on the bottom layer and then followed by low soil organic matter content, very high rainfall (388.5 mm / month) and the depth of shallow of water table and land use is mixed farms and settlements.

Lopez and Zinck (1991) states that the causes of landslides are generally less powerful rock derived from volcanic rocks and sedimentary rocks and sand-sized mixture of sand, gravel, and clay are less powerful. Furthermore, it is stated that at the beginning of the rainy season which usually occurs high rainfall intensity, so that the water content in the soil to become saturated in a short time, and coupled by a high degree of slope or steep cliffs that would increase the driving force, as well as land and generally less dense soil textured clay with great depth. Then due to deforestation caused reduced binding of ground water and the land will be easily carried away by the flow of water.

CONCLUSION AND ADVICES

Conclusion

1. The study area have hornblende hypersthyne pumiceous tuff (Qhpt) and pumiceous tuff (Qpt) which are susceptible to landslides damage.
2. The study area is classified as slightly high to high landslides danger.
3. The dominant factor that induced landslides danger are wet climate and with > 4000 mm annual rainfall, steep slope, low organic matters, sub angular blocky structure on top soil and single grain structure on the bottom and land use are dominantly coconut tree garden.
4. Community need to pay full attention to its environment in the areas. Especially, the landslides disaster controlling team during rainfall.

Advices

1. Further research about the fragile landslides areas in Padang Pariman, Agam and Tanah Datar Regence is needed.
2. It is needed alternative effort to manage the fragile landslides area in order to decrease landslides impact.
3. Community must be advised in order to be self prepared in reducing landslides impact.

Table 4: Criterium of soil characteristic landslides induced factors (Enclosed)

No		Soil Characteristic	Description	Class code
1	Solum Depth	< 25 cm	Very shallow	1
		25- 60 cm	Shallow	2
		60- 90 cm	Medium	3
		> 90 cm	Deep	4
2	Texture	S	Very coarse	1
		LS,SiS,CS	Coarse	2
		L,SL,SiL,Si	Medium	3
		C,SiC,SC	Fine	4
3	Structure	Crumb	Very good	1
		Granuler	Good	2
		Blocky, Platty, prismatic	Moderate	3
		Single grain, massive	Bad	4
4	C-Organic	> 5,01 %	Very High	1
		3,01 - 5,0 %	High	2
		2,01- 3,0 %	Moderate	3
		< 2,0 %	Low	4
5	Bulk Density	< 0,75 g/cm ³	Very Good	1
		0,75 - 1,25 g/cm ³	Good	2
		1,25 - 1,50 g/cm ³	Medium	3
		> 1,50 g/cm ³	Bad	4
6	Permeability	> 12,5 cm/hour	Very Fast	1
		6,25-12,5 cm/hour	Fast	2
		2,0-6,25 cm/hour	Medium	3
		< 2,0 cm/hour	Slow	4

Source : Zuidam (1979); Daekombe dan Gardiner (1983); Cooke dan Doorkamp (1994).

Where ; S = Sand, LS = Loamy Sand, SiS = Pasir berdebu, CS = Sandy Clay, L =Loam: SL = Sandy Loam, SiL = Silty Loam, Si = Silt, C = Clay, SC = Sandy Clay, SiC= Silty Clay.

Table 5: Criterium of Land characteristic landslide induced factors (Enclosed)

No		Land characteristics	Description	Class code
1	Slope gradien	0- 13 %	Smooth to undulating	1
		14-25 %	Sloping	2
		26 - 40 %	Slightly steep	3
		> 40 %	Steep	4
2	Length of slope	< 15 m	Shorth	1
		15-50 m	Medium	2
		50 - 250 m	Length	3
		> 250 m	Very length	4
3	Stone exposure	< 3 % of area	Nothing, few	1
		3-15 %	Medium	2
		15-90 %	Much	3
		> 90 %	Very Much	4
4	Watertable depth	> 500 m	Deep	1
		250-500 m	Medium	2
		100 -250 m	Slingthly shallow	3
		< 100 m	Shallow	4
5	Landuse	Ht (forest)	Good	1
		Sm, Kc (Bush, Mixed Garden)	Slightly Good	2
		S, Ut (sawahs, Upland)	Moderate	3
		P (resetlement)	Bad	4
6	Rainfall	> 0-30 mm /month	low	1
		30-60 mm/month	Medium	2
		60- 90 mm/month	High	3
		> 90 mm/month	Very High	4

Sources : Zuidam (1979); Daekombe dan Gardiner (1983); Cooke dan Doorkamp (1994).

Where : Ht = Forest ; Sm = Bush, Kc = Mixed Garden; S = Sawahs; Ut = Upland; P = Resettlement

Table 6: Grade Interval of landslide damage

Class	Inteval Class	Criterium of landslide damage
I	< 18	Very low
II	19-25	Low
III	26-32	Medium
IV	33-39	Slightly high
V	40-46	High
VI	>47	Very High

Source : Zuidam (1979)

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